

IMI2 821520 - ConcePTION

ConcePTION

WP3 – Determination of drug transfer and infant drug exposure during lactation: generation of quantitative and translatable data

D3.7 Validation of an animal model for lactation transfer (including translation from animal to human using available human data)

Lead contributor	Domenico Ventrella (5 - UNIBO) domenico.ventrella2@unibo.it
Other contributors	Maria Laura Bacci (5 – UNIBO)
	Alberto Elmi (5 – UNIBO)
	Monica Forni (5 – UNIBO)
	Anthony DeLise (38 – NVS)
	Nurit Ashkenazi (51 – Teva)
	Kirsten Jacobsen (49 - Ellegaard)
	Yeghig Armoudjian (20 – Bionotus)
	Johan Van Daele (20 – Bionotus)
	Pieter Annaert (7 – KUL)
	Miao-Chan Huang (7 – KUL)
	Julia Macente (7 – KUL)
	Brian Anderson (50 – LabCorp)

Document History

Version	Date	Description
V1.0	23 Oct 2023	First draft
V2.0	09 Nov 2023	UNIBO approved draft
V3.0	15 Nov 2023	WP3 approved draft
V4.0	12 Dec 2023	Final version (MB approved)
V5.0	16 Jul 2025	Version revised according to the officer's requests

Document Content

Abstract.....	4
New <i>in vivo</i> trials on Göttingen Minipigs	5
Methods.....	5
1.1 Preliminary PK study on non-pregnant, non-lactating animals.....	5
1.2 Animals, training and long-term catheter insertion.....	5
1.3 Metformin study design.....	7
1.4 Levocetirizine study design	7
1.5 Venlafaxine study design.....	8
1.6 Samplings	9
Results	9
2.1 Preliminary PK study on non-pregnant, non-lactating animals.....	9
2.2 Metformin study	12
2.3 Levocetirizine study	15
2.4 Venlafaxine study.....	18
Amoxicillin: preliminary translation from animal to human	22
Discussion and conclusions	23

Abstract

After the first *in vivo* trial performed at UNIBO using Amoxicillin as test molecule (see Deliverable 3.5), WP3 scheduled 3 additional trials using other medicines, to evaluate the performances of the model with regards to different drug classes with varying physico-chemical characteristics. The chosen medicines, out of the ones thoroughly described in Deliverable 3.1, were metformin, levocetirizine and venlafaxine. Due to the relative absence of reliable literature data regarding their use in pigs, a preliminary PK study was performed at Ellegaard Göttingen Minipigs A/S on each drug, and results were used to select the correct dosages to administer. The study design, in terms of procedures and number of samplings, was kept identical to the one tailored for the amoxicillin study. Nonetheless, for these new trials, only Göttingen Minipigs sows were used, and the timing of the samplings were modified to suit the PK profile of each medicine. The studies took place at the experimental facility of the UNIBO between January and May 2023. Trying to maximize the *in vivo* trials and grant the best translational value, each medicine was administered at two different dosages throughout the trials: low dose for lactation week 2 and 3, and high dose for lactation week 4. Metformin and levocetirizine did not induce any side effects in both sows and piglets, while venlafaxine, already at the lowest dose, induced severe alterations in sows and litters that led to trial suspension during lactation week 3 in all animals. The results were consistent across sows and litters, and seem to suggest the applicability of the model to different medicines, with different physico-chemical features.

This deliverable also shows preliminary evaluations aimed at assessing the translatability of the results obtained in Minipigs to humans. To do so, the results from the preliminary amoxicillin study were used to develop a population pharmacokinetic (popPK) model, to estimate milk/plasma ratio (M/P). Due to the lack of reliable and standardized human data, lactation Physiologically-Based Pharmacokinetic (PBPK) models were developed in this species to simulate M/P ratio. The obtained M/P ratio for pigs and humans were very close, supporting the translational value of the proposed *in vivo* model.

New *in vivo* trials on Göttingen Minipigs

Methods

1.1 Preliminary PK study on non-pregnant, non-lactating animals

Due to the relative absence of background literature data regarding the use of metformin, venlafaxine and levocetirizine in pigs, a preliminary PK study for each molecule was performed at Ellegaard Göttingen Minipigs facilities in Dalmose (DK), on Göttingen Minipigs. Since the goal was to evaluate the plasmatic levels of the medicines upon oral administration, and to comply with the 3Rs principles, such preliminary study was done on two (n=2) juvenile, non-pregnant and non-lactating animals, with body weights of 14.6 and 15.5 kg. Medicines were administered once in each animal, with a washout period of at least 96h. The dosages to be administered were chosen with the support of the pharmacologists working in WP3, based on what had been published in different species:

- metformin 125 mg (1/4 of a 500mg tablet, with feed);
- levocetirizine 5 mg (1 tablet, with feed);
- venlafaxine 25mg (1 tablet, with feed).

Blood was sampled from the jugular vein in K2 EDTA tubes at differentiated time points:

- metformin: before (0), 0.5, 1, 2, 3, 4, 6, 24h;
- levocetirizine: before (0), 0.5, 1, 2, 4, 6, 8, 24h;
- venlafaxine: before (0), 0.25, 0.5, 1, 2, 4, 6, 24h.

Upon centrifugation for plasma separation, samples were frozen and shipped to BioNotus on dry ice for medicines quantification.

1.2 Animals, training and long-term catheter insertion

The 3 *in vivo* studies described in the present document were performed at the University of Bologna on a total of 12 Göttingen Minipigs sows, 4 for each medicine. Göttingen Minipigs pregnant sows were provided by Ellegaard Göttingen Minipigs (Soroe Landevej 302 4261 Dalmose, Denmark), which contributed as the breeding facility within the project framework. All piglets included in the study were born from the above-mentioned sows in the experimental facility of the ANFI-ASA Unit, Department of Veterinary Medical Sciences, Alma Mater Studiorum – University of Bologna (via Tolara di Sopra 50, Ozzano dell'Emilia 40064 BO, Italy). Sows were transferred to the experimental facility 1 month prior to the expected delivery date (calculated based on the mating date and ultrasound pregnancy scan) and moved to the farrowing pen one week before. Animals were checked at least twice a day for health status. Farrowing was not pharmacologically induced, as this often leads to complications, but remotely assisted by trained veterinarians. Animals were fed Basic Micropigs (9AB17) pellet diet by Mucedola s.r.l. (Settimo Milanese 20019 MI, Italy), which is specialized in dedicated formulas for lab animals exclusively used for experimental purposes. Drinking water was provided *ad libitum*, while the daily feed ration was divided into two portions, early morning (7:30 am) and afternoon (3:30 pm); feed total amount was adjusted during the course of lactation, to cope with the considerable metabolic energy expenditure of the

sows. Light/dark cycle was set at 12/12h with a min Lux value during light hours of 40. Temperature was set at $21 \pm 1^\circ\text{C}$ to meet sows thermal needs. With regards to piglets, two heat lamps were placed in dedicated areas of the farrowing crate to reach $32 \pm 1^\circ\text{C}$. Piglets were individually identified with ear tags, and iron dextran (100mg; Endofer, FATRO spa) was administered IM within the first 72h of life.

Clicker training was used, as previously described in Deliverable 3.5, to reduce animal stress during the entire trial. The training protocol was set up and already started at Ellegaard facilities. Once transferred to the UNIBO experimental facility, pregnant sows were gradually accustomed to the trainers, first by just introducing a human presence in the room with food rewards; these first acclimatization steps were short (just few minutes) but were done daily, to build trust and a bonding relation. As a positive reinforcement, animals were given a food reward (apple slices, apple juice and yogurt were always very welcome). After the first week, trainers started to approach the animals to re-start the training regime already established at Ellegaard. Pregnant sows were accustomed to follow the trainers and being manipulated especially at the level of mammary glands and ears. Training sessions were short (20 min) but consistent and repeated daily (Monday-Friday). After some repetitions, the action-click-reward association became a conditioned stimulus that could keep the animals motivated to accomplish different tasks while having fun in the meantime. During the training sessions, all the animals showed well-being associated activities, and, after the routine was established, they were easily manipulated and seemed to enjoy the training session, an additional occasion to get out of the cage and explore the environment.

Long-term catheters were used to allow the possibility to repeatedly collect blood from sows, without having to puncture them. The insertion procedure was thoroughly described in Deliverable 3.5. The procedure was done towards the end of the first lactation week, upon deep sedation achieved by an intramuscular injection of Tiletamine/Zolazepam 3.5-5 mg/kg (Zoletil 50/50 Virbac srl). Oxygen was provided during the procedure through a breathing mask. During the entire duration of the procedure, which always lasted less than 60 min, support fluid therapy (Ringer Lactate 10 ml/kg/h) and the usual anaesthesia monitoring were provided (ETCO₂, SpO₂, Temperature, ECG, NIBP). Catheterizations were performed following standard surgical sterility guidelines: clipped, neat, disinfected area dedicated, sterile surgical draping, gloves and instruments (packed and autoclaved for each animal); surgical field prep consisted of 3 alternating scrubs of a chlorhexidine scrubbing solution and 70% alcohol. Seldinger's over-the-wire technique was employed for peripheral auricular vein catheterization: the vessel was punctured with a dedicated sharp hollow needle which was then removed with the plastic sheath left in place to allow the guidewire to be advanced through it for at least 30mm. Once the wire was inserted without major resistance, the sheath was removed and replaced with a vessel dilator. Finally, upon dilator removal, the catheter was slid over the wire and into the vein, sutured to the skin and further fixed by means of an IV securement dressing integrated with chlorhexidine gluconate gel pad (Tegaderm CHG, 3M). Heparinized saline (300IU/ml) was used as lock solution to ensure patency on a daily bases and after every blood collection. Catheter sets were purchased by Mila International: MILACATH Guidewire (SA1925) - Single Lumen - 19Ga (3.5Fr) x 25cm (10in).

1.3 Metformin study design

Based on the results of the preliminary PK study performed at Ellegaard, the WP3 contributing scientists decided to administer metformin at 2 different dosages: a lower one for the first 2 weeks of trial similar to the one used for the preliminary PKs, and a higher one to try and reach plasmatic concentrations as similar as possible to humans:

- 500 mg/day in a single oral administration for lactation weeks 2 and 3 (low dose; 1 tablet 500 mg)
- 850 mg/day in a single oral administration for lactation week 4 (high dose; 1 tablet 850 mg)

In this specific case, the timepoints for the PK analysis performed on the first dosing day were:

- Before (0)
- 0.5h after administration
- 1h after administration
- 2h after administration
- 3h after administration
- 4h after administration
- 6h after administration
- 8h after administration
- 24h after administration

As for the rest of the study design, the trial was divided into SOW DAYS and SOW+PIGLET DAYS:

- SOW DAY (twice a week for 3 weeks): matched blood/milk samplings on the sows before administration and 1, 3 and 6h after;
- SOW+PIGLET DAY (twice a week for 3 weeks): matched blood/milk samplings on the sows before administration and 4h after, and piglets blood collection 25 min after both maternal samplings.

1.4 Levocetirizine study design

Based on the results of the preliminary PK study performed at Ellegaard Göttingen Minipigs, the WP3 contributing scientists decided to administer levocetirizine at 2 different dosages: a lower one for the first 2 weeks of trial similar to the one used for the preliminary PKs, and a higher one to try and reach plasmatic concentrations as similar as possible to humans:

- 15 mg/day in a single oral administration for lactation weeks 2 and 3 (low dose; 3 tablets 5mg each)
- 40 mg/day in a single oral administration for lactation week 4 (high dose; 8 tablets 5mg each)

In this specific case, the timepoints for the PK analysis performed on the first dosing day were:

- Before (0)
- 0.5h after administration
- 1h after administration

- 2h after administration
- 3h after administration
- 4h after administration
- 6h after administration
- 8h after administration
- 24h after administration

As for the rest of the study design, the trial was divided into SOW DAYS and SOW+PIGLETS DAYS:

- SOW DAY (twice a week for 3 weeks): matched blood/milk samplings on the sows before administration and 1, 3 and 6h after;
- SOW+PIGLET DAY (twice a week for 3 weeks): matched blood/milk samplings on the sows before administration and 4h after, and piglets blood collection 25 min after both maternal samplings.

1.5 Venlafaxine study design

Based on the results of the preliminary PK study performed at Ellegaard Göttingen Minipigs, the WP3 contributing scientists decided to administered venlafaxine at 2 different dosages: a lower one for the first 2 weeks of trial similar to the one used for the preliminary PKs, and a higher one to try and reach plasmatic concentrations as similar as possible to humans:

- 75 mg/day in a single oral administration for lactation weeks 2 and 3 (low dose; 1 tablet 75mg)
- 375 mg/day in a single oral administration for lactation week 4 (high dose; 5 tablets 75mg each)

In this specific case, the timepoints for the PK analysis performed on the first dosing day were:

- Before (0)
- 0.5h after administration
- 1h after administration
- 2h after administration
- 3h after administration
- 4h after administration
- 6h after administration
- 8h after administration
- 24h after administration

As for the rest of the study design, the trial was divided into SOW DAYS and SOW+PIGLETS DAYS:

- SOW DAY (twice a week for 3 weeks): matched blood/milk samplings on the sows before administration and 1, 3 and 6h after;
- SOW+PIGLET DAY (twice a week for 3 weeks): matched blood/milk samplings on the sows

1.6 Samplings

Blood samplings from sows were carried out relatively easily due to the previously described training: animals, distracted by the food reward and accustomed to being touched on the ears, did not care about the operator collecting blood from the catheter. The latter allowed for a pivotal refinement of the study as no pain was involved in this procedure. Blood was collected into EDTA tubes, upon elimination of the residual lock solution within the catheter lumen together with the first ml of blood to avoid contamination. Right afterwards, the catheter was flushed with saline solution and locked again with heparinized saline. The procedure was always performed by two operators, one in charge of providing the animal with the reward (usually apple juice) and the second working on the catheter. Samples were immediately centrifuged (15min, 1800 x g, 4°C) to obtain plasma, which was divided into 500µl aliquots and stored at -80°C.

To avoid excessive stress in piglets, blood was collected from the femoral artery upon light sedation achieved by means of Sevoflurane administered through a breathing mask in 100% O₂. In order to allow for the potential medicines present in milk to be absorbed into piglets' bloodstream, the samplings were actually performed 30 min after maternal samplings (that always coincided with nursing).

As for milk samples, the procedure was much more challenging, since the ejection period is very short in pigs and happens only upon intense stimulation of the udder by the litter. Considering the operators would have to wait for the piglets jostling and nuzzling on the mammary glands to induce oxytocin release, pivotal for milk ejection, the research team decided to administer sows with exogenous oxytocin (2-3 IU, IV administration). This allowed for more precise samplings in terms of timing as matched blood/milk collection was required for this preliminary study. The udders were cleaned using an antibacterial soap and warm water to avoid gross contamination of the samples. Milking was performed manually, as fast as possible, and directly along the length of the sow's nipple; indeed, massaging the udder does not allow for a good sampling and, as of today, no commercial mechanical devices are available for the chosen species. During the collection of the milk samples, piglets were not separated from the sow, therefore the operators had to compete with the litter to access a teat. Fortunately, piglets tend to establish a preference for a given nipple during the first lactation days, and only aim at that one when nursing. This allowed the operators to know, for each sow, where to collect from. During the training sessions, sows were encouraged to step with the forelimbs on a small stepbench to lift the more cranial udders, making access a little bit easier. This was not always done during the actual milk samplings, since sows prefer to nurse while laying on one side. Milk samples were immediately placed on ice, aliquoted as for plasma and stored at -80°C. At the end of the trials, samples were shipped on dry ice to BioNotus for medicines quantification.

Results

2.1 Preliminary PK study on non-pregnant, non-lactating animals

The results of the metformin preliminary PK study (dose: 125mg) are reported in Table 1 and represented in Figure 1.

Table 1. Quantified concentrations of metformin in Gottingen Minipigs juvenile animals (n=2)

Timepoint (h)	METFORMIN	
	Animal 1 (ng/mL)	Animal 2 (ng/mL)
0	0.000	0.000
0.5	224.652	729.120
1	455.367	816.716
2	436.592	695.641
3	311.452	435.826
4	198.767	265.642
6	70.257	112.794
24	17.177	15.473

Figure 1. Preliminary metformin PK study on juvenile Gottingen Minipigs (n=2). Administered dose: 125mg, OS.

The results of the levocetirizine preliminary PK study (dose: 5mg) are reported in Table 2 and represented in Figure 2.

Table 2. Quantified concentrations of levocetirizine in Gottingen Minipigs juvenile animals (n=2)

Timepoint (h)	LEVOCETIRIZINE	
	Animal 1 (ng/mL)	Animal 2 (ng/mL)
0	0.000	0.000
0.25	70.158	207.899
0.5	105.068	210.451
1	139.449	183.042
2	168.685	174.640
4	122.919	123.146
24	6.175	5.941

Figure 2. Preliminary levocetirizine PK study on juvenile Gottingen Minipigs (n=2). Administered dose: 5mg, OS.

The results of the venlafaxine preliminary PK study (dose: 25mg) are reported in Table 3 and represented in Figure 3. In this case, also its main metabolite O-desmethyl venlafaxine was quantified.

Table 3. Quantified concentrations of venlafaxine and O-desmethyl venlafaxine in Gottingen Minipigs juvenile animals (n=2)

Timepoint (h)	VENLAFAXINE		O-DESMETHYL VENLAFAXINE	
	Animal 1 (ng/mL)	Animal 2 (ng/mL)	Animal 1 (ng/mL)	Animal 2 (ng/mL)
0	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000
0.5	24.834	16.203	5.652	16.399
1	23.325	16.379	8.270	18.053
2	7.695	10.888	11.179	14.289
4	1.824	4.349	11.654	20.582
6	0.000	2.298	13.924	20.096
8	2.010	2.407	18.364	17.278
24	0.000	1.859	3.101	9.082

Figure 3. Preliminary venlafaxine PK study on juvenile Gottingen Minipigs (n=2). Administered dose: 25mg, OS.

2.2 Metformin study

Metformin was quantifiable in all maternal samples, aside from the ones collected before the first dosing, as expected. The determination range of Metformin was 2 – 1600 ng/ml.

The results of the plasmatic PK study performed on sows on the first day of metformin dosing (low dose, 500 mg/day) are represented in Figure 4.

Figure 4. Quantification of metformin in sow's plasma upon first dosing (low dose, 500 mg/day). The graph represents the mean value; error bars indicate the standard error of the mean (SEM)

Descriptive statistics for the quantification of metformin into maternal plasma and milk samples are reported in Table 4 and 5 respectively.

Table 4. Metformin quantification (ng/ml) in maternal plasma samples. Low dose was administered for 2 week, the high one for 1 week.

		<i>n</i>	Min ng/ml	Max ng/ml	Mean ng/ml	SEM ng/ml
Low dose 500 mg/day	Pre-metformin	27	0	509.5	58.89	18.57
	1h post	13	225.9	3032	1423	215.8
	3h post	13	411.3	2156	1248	148.4
	4h post	13	429.5	1792	1075	131.4
	6h post	14	67.18	939.6	487.2	68.01
High dose 850 mg/day	Pre-metformin	11	39.74	193.4	107.4	15.62
	1h post	5	133.7	3090	1393	561.7
	3h post	6	106.9	2484	1032	434.7
	4h post	5	361.8	3087	1372	544.3
	6h post	6	118.8	1145	656.2	180.3

Table 5. Metformin quantification (ng/ml) in maternal milk samples. Low dose was administered for 2 week, the high one for 1 week.

		<i>n</i>	Min ng/ml	Max ng/ml	Mean ng/ml	SEM ng/ml
Low dose	Pre-metformin	29	0	290.5	139.1	14.69

500 mg/day	1h post	14	41.42	581	206.4	36.01
	3h post	14	263.3	1090	523.9	72.00
	4h post	15	149.4	1319	579.3	100.5
	6h post	14	169.4	1041	490.8	63.48
High dose 850 mg/day	Pre-metformin	16	103	468.8	267.9	28.44
	1h post	8	164.1	629.2	331.5	52.87
	3h post	8	162.5	596	403.9	50.77
	4h post	8	171.5	1050	432.4	97.39
	6h post	8	272.3	1187	518.2	106.8

Figure 5 represents the trends of the concentrations of metformin in maternal plasma, firstly data divided per dose and then together. The first two panels also report the results of the statistical analysis (Kruskal-Wallis test followed by the multiple comparisons post-hoc test) performed to assess differences between timepoints within the same dosing regimen. For both administered dosages, the plasmatic peak was recorded 1h after administration, with a statistically relevant difference in comparison to the pre-metformin timepoint. Looking at the high dosage, it can be noticed how the intermediate point (3h post) seems to not follow the gradual descending trend of the medicine, probably due to the relatively low sample size.

Figure 5. Graphical representation of the concentrations of metformin in sows' plasma upon oral administration. The first two panels are divided per dose and report statistical differences (different letters indicate differences between timepoints, $p < 0.05$); the last panel shows all plasma data combined.

Accordingly, Figure 6 shows the results of the quantification in milk, with the same approach described above for plasma. In this case, the highest metformin concentration were recorded 4h after administration of the low dose, and 6h after administration of the high one.

Figure 6. Graphical representation of the concentrations of metformin in sows’ milk upon oral administration. The first two panels are divided per dose and report statistical differences (different letters indicate differences between timepoints, $p < 0.05$); the last panel shows all milk data combined.

As for piglets’ plasma, metformin was quantifiable in 43 out of 64 samples. No statistical differences were recorded upon comparison between samples collected before maternal administration and the ones collected 4h post-maternal administration. It is important to remind that, according to the study design, sows were constantly dosed from the first up to the last day of trial. Therefore, the medicine levels detected in piglets blood collected before the daily maternal administration reflect the fact that, after first dosing, milk always shows a certain medicine quantity. Figure 7 shows the metformin level in piglets’ plasma at both timepoints, divided per maternal dosing (low dose 500 mg/day; high dose 850 mg/day) and also the comparison with the pertinent maternal milk levels. Despite metformin being present in the majority of piglets’ samples, its levels are extremely low when compared to the one quantified in the corresponding maternal milk.

Figure 7. Metformin levels in piglets’ plasma collected before and 4h after maternal administration and comparison with corresponding milk levels.

2.3 Levocetirizine study

Out of the 4 pregnant sows shipped for the levocetirizine trial, one delivered non-viable piglets 8 days before the anticipated farrowing date. This trial was therefore carried out with 3 sows and 3 litters.

Levocetirizine was quantifiable in all maternal samples, aside from the ones collected before the first dosing, as expected. The determination ranges of levocetirizine were 1 – 1000 ng/mL.

The results of the plasmatic PK study performed on sows on the first day of levocetirizine dosing (low dose, 15 mg/day) are represented in Figure 8.

Figure 8. Quantification of levocetirizine in sow's plasma upon first dosing (low dose, 15 mg/day). The graph represents the mean value; error bars indicate the standard error of the mean (SEM)

Descriptive statistics for the quantification of levocetirizine into maternal plasma and milk samples are reported in Table 6 and 7 respectively. During this trial, 2 vascular catheters lost patency right before the passage to the higher dose, therefore the number of plasmatic samples in this case is low (Table 6), and was included in the descriptive statistics but not into the inferential one. Nonetheless, animals continued the trial, received the higher dosage and milk was still collected.

Table 6. Levocetirizine quantification (ng/ml) in maternal plasma samples. Low dose was administered for 2 week, the high one for 1 week.

		<i>n</i>	Min ng/ml	Max ng/ml	Mean ng/ml	SEM ng/ml
Low dose 15 mg/day	Pre-levocetirizine	19	15.26	183.8	65.46	10.16
	1h post	9	92.57	376.6	181.3	30.3
	3h post	10	71.95	454.9	279.1	41.51
	4h post	9	97.55	613.5	336.4	62.03
	6h post	10	49.1	577.3	238	46.2
High dose 40 mg/day	Pre-levocetirizine	3	30.32	102.4	63.86	20.95
	1h post	1	112.1	112.1	112.1	/

	3h post	1	116.5	116.5	116.5	/
	4h post	0	/	/	/	/
	6h post	1	106.1	106.1	106.1	/

Table 7. Levocetirizine quantification (ng/ml) in maternal milk samples. Low dose was administered for 2 week, the high one for 1 week.

		<i>n</i>	Min ng/ml	Max ng/ml	Mean ng/ml	SEM ng/ml
Low dose 15 mg/day	Pre-levocetirizine	25	0	185.6	33.25	8.621
	1h post	11	20.68	141.7	58.47	10.47
	3h post	12	29.29	156.3	74.6	10.26
	4h post	11	29.01	145.6	76.94	10.92
	6h post	12	22.99	100.6	52.84	7.354
High dose 40 mg/day	Pre-levocetirizine	7	21.29	414.3	146.1	55.59
	1h post	3	36.24	269.2	179.5	72.39
	3h post	3	27.99	356.5	220.4	98.91
	4h post	2	281.9	511.6	396.8	114.9
	6h post	3	31.29	364.2	223.8	99.58

Figure 9 represents the trends of the concentrations of levocetirizine in maternal plasma, only for the low dosing regimen; the results of the statistical analysis (Kruskal-Wallis test followed by the multiple comparisons post-hoc test) performed to assess differences between timepoints are also included. The plasmatic peak was recorded 4h after administration, with all timepoints being statistically different when compared to the pre-levocetirizine one.

Figure 9. Graphical representation of the concentrations of levocetirizine in sows' plasma upon oral administration (different letters indicate differences between timepoints, $p < 0.05$).

Figure 10 shows the results of the quantification of levocetirizine in milk, firstly data divided per dose and then together. The first two panels also report the results of the statistical analysis (Kruskal-Wallis test followed by the multiple comparisons post-hoc test) performed to assess differences between timepoints within the same

dosing regimen. In both cases, the highest levocetirizine concentration were recorded 4h after administration of both doses, with a more marked increase in the higher dose (despite the lack of statistical difference, most likely due to the poor sample size).

Figure 10. Graphical representation of the concentrations of levocetirizine in sows' milk upon oral administration. The first two panels are divided per dose and report statistical differences (different letters indicate differences between timepoints, $p < 0.05$); the last panel shows all milk data combined.

As for piglets' plasma, levocetirizine was quantifiable in 45 out of 51 samples. No statistical differences were recorded upon comparison between samples collected before maternal administration and the ones collected 4h post-maternal administration. Figure 11 shows the levocetirizine level in piglets' plasma at both timepoints, divided per maternal dosing (low dose 15 mg/day; high dose 40 mg/day) and the comparison with the pertinent maternal milk levels. Despite levocetirizine being present in the majority of piglets' samples, its levels are extremely low when compared to the one quantified in the corresponding maternal milk.

Figure 11. Levocetirizine levels in piglets' plasma collected before and 4h after maternal administration and comparison with corresponding milk levels.

2.4 Venlafaxine study

For the venlafaxine study, it was decided to quantify both venlafaxine and its main metabolite O-desmethyl venlafaxine (ODV). Determination ranges of Venlafaxine and O-Desmethyl venlafaxine were 0.5 – 500 ng/mL.

During the venlafaxine study, all enrolled sows started showing behavioural alterations such as lethargy after the first week of dosing, that evolved in severe gait alteration. The inability to stand up and safely reach feed and water was included as one of the indications, in the ethical protocol approved by the Italian Ministry of Health, to suspend dosing and interrupt the study. At the same time, piglets started showing gastrointestinal alterations such as diarrhoea and lack of appetite. Therefore, the study was suspended (during the low dose regimen, 75 mg/day). Already 24h after interruption of dosing, the sows started recovering and were able to stand up, eat and drink, and went back to normal after 2 days.

The results of the plasmatic PK study performed on sows on the first day of venlafaxine dosing (low dose, 75 mg/day) are represented in Figure 12.

Figure 12. Quantification of venlafaxine and O-desmethyl venlafaxine in sow's plasma upon first dosing (low dose, 75 mg/day). The graph represents the mean value; error bars indicate the standard error of the mean (SEM)

Descriptive statistics for the quantification of venlafaxine and ODV into maternal plasma and milk samples are reported in Table 8 and 9 respectively. As previously indicated, data only refer to the low dosing regime (75 mg/day).

Table 8. Venlafaxine and ODV quantification (ng/ml) in maternal plasma samples.

		VENLAFAXINE				
		<i>n</i>	Min ng/ml	Max ng/ml	Mean ng/ml	SEM ng/ml
Low Dose 75 mg/day	Pre-venlafaxine	23	0	137.3	35.53	7.95
	1h post	12	2.914	102	40.29	10.63
	3h post	12	8.998	234.5	79.76	19.03
	4h post	11	10.93	305.4	135.1	33.38
	6h post	11	11.74	298.9	78.8	25.53
		O-DESMETHYL VENLAFAXINE				
		<i>n</i>	Min ng/ml	Max ng/ml	Mean ng/ml	SEM ng/ml
	Pre-venlafaxine	23	2.777	132.5	50.71	8.572
	1h post	12	17.28	97.88	51.24	8.101
	3h post	12	36.37	171.6	80.24	11.56
	4h post	11	31.36	198.2	102.8	16.16
	6h post	11	31.5	204.1	77.74	14.39

Table 9. Venlafaxine and ODV quantification (ng/ml) in maternal milk samples.

		VENLAFAXINE				
		<i>n</i>	Min ng/ml	Max ng/ml	Mean ng/ml	SEM ng/ml
Low Dose	Pre-venlafaxine	28	6.796	251.7	75.17	14.21

75 mg/day	1h post	17	4.353	306	89.96	20.74
	3h post	17	17	542.9	167.2	42.35
	4h post	11	0.5328	1289	372.6	114.8
	6h post	13	33.25	870.7	278.1	72.95
	O-DESMETHYL VENLAFAXINE					
		<i>n</i>	Min ng/ml	Max ng/ml	Mean ng/ml	SEM ng/ml
	Pre-venlafaxine	24	10.84	222	114	13.24
	1h post	13	41	272.8	134.3	20.7
	3h post	13	94.09	488	205	29.8
	4h post	11	1.47	595	257.7	56.28
	6h post	13	75.58	483.5	237.4	35.26

Figure 13 represents the trends of the concentrations of venlafaxine and ODV in maternal plasma, only for the low dosing regimen (75 mg/day); the results of the statistical analysis (Kruskal-Wallis test followed by the multiple comparisons post-hoc test) performed to assess differences between timepoints are also included. The plasmatic peak was recorded 4h after administration for both venlafaxine and its main metabolite.

Figure 13. Graphical representation of the concentrations of venlafaxine (A) and ODV (B) in sows' plasma upon oral administration (different letters indicate differences between timepoints, $p < 0.05$).

Figure 14 represents the trend of the medicine and its metabolite in milk samples. The behaviour of venlafaxine and ODV is identical in milk, with a marked peak four hours after administration.

Figure 14. Graphical representation of the concentrations of venlafaxine (A) and ODV (B) in sows' milk upon oral administration (different letters indicate differences between timepoints, p<0.05).

As for piglets, venlafaxine itself was always below the lower limit of detection, while O-desmethyl venlafaxine was quantifiable in 22 out of 30 samples. The levels of ODV in piglets' plasma are represented in Figure 15, alongside the comparison with the corresponding levels in milk. Also in this case, piglets' exposure seems to be extremely low.

Figure 15. O-desmethyl venlafaxine levels in piglets' plasma collected before and 4h after maternal administration and comparison with corresponding milk levels.

Amoxicillin: preliminary translation from animal to human

A population Pharmacokinetic (popPK) model was developed with the plasma and milk data of amoxicillin in lactating Göttingen Minipigs from the study conducted by UNIBO. The PK of amoxicillin in the lactation Göttingen Minipigs can be described by a two-compartment model. To reflect amoxicillin's milk transfer, the milk-to-plasma (M/P) ratio was estimated by dividing the area-under-the-curve within a dosing interval in milk by the one in plasma. The model-simulated M/P ratio for a virtual Göttingen Minipig population (1000 individuals) was 0.14, corresponding to 0.9-fold the M/P ratio (0.153) calculated with the study data. For humans, lactation Physiologically-Based Pharmacokinetic (PBPK) models were developed on two different software platforms using a bottom-up approach by associating amoxicillin's physicochemical properties and human system data. PBPK-based simulations were performed for a virtual lactation population (10 trials X 10 individuals). With Simcyp® (Certara), the simulated M/P was 0.17, while with PK-SIM (Open Systems Pharmacology), the predicted M/P was 0.15. It is worth noting that the predicted M/P values were comparable between the Göttingen Minipig PopPK model and the human PBPK models.

Discussion and conclusions

The three *in vivo* studies conducted on Göttingen Minipig sows represent a significant extension of the preliminary work performed with amoxicillin, enabling testing of the proposed preclinical model on drugs belonging to different therapeutic classes and with diverse physicochemical properties. The use of metformin, levocetirizine, and venlafaxine allowed for an assessment of the model's robustness and its potential translatability to humans, both in terms of maternal pharmacokinetics and milk transfer.

For metformin and levocetirizine, the model demonstrated suitability and tolerance, with no clinically relevant adverse effects observed in either sows or piglets. In both cases, plasma and milk concentration profiles aligned with expectations, showing pharmacokinetic peaks at approximately 1 hour (plasma) and 4–6 hours (milk) post-administration, confirming the protocol's reproducibility. Although drug levels in piglet plasma were generally low, their presence confirms transfer via maternal milk and provides valuable data on neonatal exposure. In contrast, venlafaxine exhibited significant toxicity even at relatively low doses, causing severe neurological and gastrointestinal adverse effects in both sows and piglets, which necessitated the early termination of the trial. This finding highlights the model's utility not only for pharmacokinetic evaluation, but also for the early identification of potential safety concerns related to lactation. Moreover, the concurrent quantification of the active metabolite, O-desmethylvenlafaxine, provided a more comprehensive understanding of the drug's pharmacological profile.

Methodologically, the use of long-term catheters, a positive-reinforcement training approach, and a standardized experimental design across all compounds were significant strengths of the protocol. The ability to collect serial samples under minimal stress conditions improved data quality and enhanced the reliability of the results.

Finally, the consistency between Göttingen Minipigs results and those simulated using lactation PBPK models in humans (for estimating milk-to-plasma ratios) further supports the translational validity of this *in vivo* model. Similar M/P ratios between the two species suggest that the Göttingen Minipigs can provide a realistic predictive system for studying drug transfer into human breast milk.

In conclusion, the proposed preclinical model shows strong potential for analyzing drug transfer into milk and neonatal exposure, delivering both pharmacokinetic and safety data of regulatory relevance. Future studies, including additional compounds and simulated clinical conditions, will further strengthen its validation and applicability in regulatory contexts.